

MULBERRY TREE: A VALUABLE GIFT OF NATURE**Sadigova D.O.***Faculty of Chemistry and Biology,
teacher Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University***Abstract**

The mulberry tree (*Morus* spp.) is a widely distributed and economically significant plant with substantial ecological and nutritional value. This study highlights the biological characteristics, diversity, and practical importance of mulberry species, particularly in Azerbaijan. Special attention is given to its role in agriculture, sericulture, environmental protection, and human health.

Keywords: mulberry tree, fruit, leaf, medicine, vitamin, silk

The mulberry tree is one of the widely distributed plants in nature and has great importance in human life. Belonging to the Moraceae family, this tree mainly grows in temperate and subtropical climate zones and is also широко распространен in Azerbaijan. The mulberry tree plays an important role both in natural ecosystems and in agriculture.

There are 17 species of mulberry in the world, and 3 in Azerbaijan: *Morus alba* L. (white mulberry), *Morus nigra* L. (black mulberry), and *Morus rubra* L. (red mulberry). These species differ from each other in the color, taste, and ripening time of their fruits. Through folk selection, a number of high-quality new mulberry varieties have been developed in Azerbaijan, such as Shahtut, Bedana mulberry, Khar mulberry, Ganja mulberry, Shirvan mulberry, etc.

Researchers at the Institute of Genetics and Selection of ANAS have created new mulberry varieties such as Zarif mulberry, Azeri mulberry, Khanlar mulberry, Firudin mulberry, Yagub mulberry, Emin mulberry, Zakir mulberry, and Gozel mulberry, which produce 2–3 times more leaf yield than local wild varieties using various breeding methods.

The most valuable part of the mulberry tree is its fruit. Mulberry fruits can be white, black, or red. These fruits are rich in vitamins, especially vitamin C, B-group vitamins, and various minerals. In addition, they contain different antioxidants that are important for the human body. Regular consumption of mulberry fruits strengthens the immune system and improves overall health.

The leaves of the mulberry tree are also very important. As is known, the silkworm feeds only on mulberry leaves. Therefore, the mulberry tree forms the basis of the silk industry. Without mulberry leaves, silk production would not be possible. Sericulture has developed throughout history in many countries, including Azerbaijan, and has played an important economic role. The cultivation of mulberry trees is essential for the sustainable development of this field.

The mulberry tree is a long-lived and resilient plant. Its root system is well developed, penetrating

deep into the soil, preventing erosion, and contributing to environmental improvement. Its trunk is thick and strong. Mulberry wood is used in some household and craft applications.

Various food products are made from mulberry fruits. They are used to prepare jam, syrup, dried fruits, and other delicious products. In folk medicine, both the fruits and leaves of the mulberry tree are used to treat various diseases.

Planting mulberry orchards along roads in Azerbaijan is a commendable practice. Establishing mulberry plantations along field borders and in unused riverbed areas is important for the future. The role of mulberry in solving food problems, its use as a medicinal resource, and its contribution to air purification should be highly appreciated.

Currently, meliorative greening works are being carried out around main canals and collectors in our republic. For this purpose, mulberry planting is widely used.

Creating forest belts, establishing forest massifs, expanding its use as an ornamental plant in residential areas, and developing productive modern varieties of this beneficial plant are among the important tasks.

Conclusion: The mulberry tree is a highly beneficial plant both economically and ecologically. Its protection and widespread cultivation are of great importance for the well-being of society.

References

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